

FAIRCORE4EOSC
Core Components Supporting a FAIR EOSC

FAIRCORE4EOSC Services

CAT

Compliance Assessment Toolkit

Partners working on this component

Component Overview

Quality assurance is a fundamental part of mature service provision, and during such quality assurance processes, assessment of compliance with a variety of norms and standards as well as end user expectations are typically involved. Compliance can be evaluated or assessed in formal or informal ways, and the results can be adjudicated internally, or by way of external review or audit - these are all variations of the same fundamental process.

Compliance assessment should be an integral part of e-infrastructure provision in general, and specifically should apply to quality assurance in the field of research data management - ensuring that the systems, services, and functionality provided to the community meet the relevant norms and expectations. While relevant norms and associated quality assurance frameworks exist for digital systems in general (ISO 27001, ITIL, etc.), compliance assessment in respect of other considerations in the landscape is relatively poorly developed.

The Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT), while aimed at the operational assessment of EOSC PID Policy compliance (and derivations based on the policy) was purposely designed and implemented to be reusable in many contexts, including current and emerging sets of quality assurance needs in the landscape. These cover, but are not limited to, aspects such as community expectations (FAIR, TRUST, and CARE), EOSC alignment (node entry requirements, interoperability frameworks, rules of participation), and formal specifications (e.g. participation in AAI federations). The CAT is operationally available for PID Policy compliance assessments, and work on beta releases for FAIR and AAI federation assessments are under way.

Functionalities

The Compliance Assessment Toolkit provides a platform for the standardised encoding, recording, publication, and querying of compliance. Long-term persistence of assessments is also supported. The toolkit links assessment to best practices, guidance, specifications, and recommendations, assisting end users not only to determine a level of performance against a benchmark, but also to identify steps towards improvement.

The operational instance of CAT - focused on PID Policy Compliance - allows casual users to search for and find assessments, obtain PID selection and appraisal support via the PID Knowledge Base, and integrate read-only API services into external systems. Validated users can perform, edit, and publish assessments, and curators (administrators) can assist end users and institutions with the development and deployment of custom PID policies. These can, in turn, be used to validate the compliance of institutions and services against the custom policy.

Impact

The CAT is expected to have a significant impact on evaluation, appraisal, and assessment-related tasks and requirements in the context of EOSC. There is a pervasive problem in the research landscape, in that alignment, compliance, or fulfilment are often claimed without any public evidence. It is, for example, common to claim FAIR compliance, alignment with TRUST principles, or support for Open Science without any verifiable evidence that such claims are based on a consistent and repeatable process of assessment. CAT addresses this by standardising and harmonising compliance assessment, and by making a public record of compliance available for the long term. In doing so, it directly supports quality assurance in EOSC and beyond.

Discover the
CAT tool

DTR

Data Type Registry

Partners working on this component

Component Overview

The Data Type Registry (DTR) is a production-ready service developed under the FAIRCORE4EOSC project to support data interoperability and reuse in line with the FAIR principles. It offers a sustainable framework for the registration, discovery, and long-term management of structured, machine-readable data type definitions. Through the DTR, research communities can define and share standardized data structures that improve data quality, facilitate reuse, and support cross-disciplinary research.

The DTR helps researchers and data providers ensure that their data is well-documented, understandable, and reusable by others. By enabling the publication of consistent and versioned data type definitions, it supports the creation of high-quality metadata and fosters interoperability across diverse datasets and research infrastructures. The DTR also offers tools for validating data against registered type definitions, allowing automated checks for data quality and structural consistency, which is critical for ensuring reliable research outcomes.

Accessible via an intuitive web interface and programmatic APIs, the DTR accommodates both manual and automated workflows. Users can easily create, search, and manage data types, while developers can integrate its functionalities into data pipelines and services. It integrates with federated identity systems for secure, seamless access and supports fine-grained access control and ownership management for registered types, promoting collaborative management and long-term stewardship.

The DTR is openly available, GDPR-compliant, and maintained to ensure long-term availability under Persistent Identifiers for eResearch (ePIC) governance, ensuring that type definitions remain accessible and resolvable over time.

Functionalities

The Data Type Registry (DTR) enables users to define, manage, and share structured data type definitions to improve data interoperability. It supports the full lifecycle of type definitions, including creation, metadata enrichment, versioning, discovery, and validation. Users can define data types through a web interface, following guided workflows to specify metadata, structural properties, and constraints.

For automated processes, the DTR offers RESTful APIs, allowing integration with data pipelines and external services. Data types can be versioned, and categorized using taxonomy nodes for easier discovery. Access controls ensure that type definitions can be managed collaboratively or restricted as needed.

The DTR also supports schema generation, translating type definitions into machine-readable schemas used for validating data structures. This ensures that datasets conform to defined types, supporting automated quality checks. Persistent identifiers assigned to each type guarantee long-term reference and discoverability, making type definitions actionable in both human and machine contexts.

Through these capabilities, the DTR provides a structured, interoperable environment for managing complex data descriptions and enabling their reuse across research domains.

Impact

The Data Type Registry (DTR) significantly enhances data interoperability and reuse by enabling the creation and sharing of standardised, machine-readable data type definitions. It empowers research communities to align their data structures with common standards, improving data quality and supporting cross-disciplinary collaboration. By facilitating clear documentation and validation of data formats, the DTR helps ensure that data is both understandable and actionable by humans and machines. This reduces duplication of effort, lowers integration barriers, and fosters more efficient data sharing across projects and domains. As a sustainable, open service integrated into the broader EOSC ecosystem, the DTR contributes directly to advancing FAIR data practices, helping researchers maximise the value and long-term impact of their data assets.

Discover the
DTR Service

MSCR

Metadata Schema & Crosswalk Registry

Partners working on this component

Component Overview

MSCR is a registry to support research data management, which allows registered users and communities to create, register and version meta data schemas and crosswalks with resolvable identifiers. The published content can be searched, browsed and downloaded without restrictions. It also provides an API to facilitate the management of contents and transformation of data from one schema to another via registered crosswalks.

The key focus of MSCR are:

Providing a registry for existing schemas and crosswalks, creating a tool for defining and describing crosswalks between existing schemas, and **facilitating the transformation of (meta)data documents** using crosswalks created with the MSCR.

The implemented MSCR service contributes to the FAIRness of research related data by making its metadata (schemas) more findable and accessible, it promotes discoverability, accessibility and re-usability of crosswalks through uniquely identified, uniform and structured mapping sets, and allows crosswalk specifications to be made directly interoperable through artefacts generated for crosswalk operationalisation.

Functionalities

1. Registration of schemas and crosswalks in multiple formats. The supported formats currently are CSV, XSD, JSON Schema, RDFS, SHACL, OWL, SKOS. ENUM and PDF for schemas and SSSOM, Simple Table, XSLT and PDF for crosswalks.
2. Basic content management support like resolvable handles, rich metadata, versioning and provenance information.
3. Crosswalk Editor for visually creating crosswalks between metadata schemas
4. Generation of executable versions of crosswalks (e.g. XSLT) to support (meta)data transformation.
5. Content creation and management through APIs.
6. Integration with Data Type Registry (DTR) to provide custom data types for the metadata schemas and Vocabulary Service to map attribute values to specific vocabularies.
7. Notification service to allow users to subscribe to content changes.
8. Integration with B2Access AAI for easy authentication.

Impact

The MSCR facilitates interoperability between information systems on a semantic and technical levels through discoverable, accessible and actionable schemas and crosswalks. By providing an easy to use GUI for creating crosswalks, the MSCR attracts users currently relying on project specific solutions for implementing (meta)data mappings. The MSCR works on data schemas, vocabularies and other semantic artefacts and encourages organisations and individual researchers to share, use and reuse crosswalks in a way that can make previously hard to find interoperability work in research related workflows visible in a uniform way (FAIRification).

Discover the
MSCR Service

PIDGraph

PID Graph

Partners working on this component

Component Overview

The PIDGraph services are designed to facilitate the exposure and usage of Persistent Identifier (PID) metadata and connections, centered around a trusted source - in this instance, the core data of the graph is made up of Digital Object Identifier (DOI) metadata held by DataCite, one of the main DOI Registration Agencies (RAs), and the network of the graph is built around the relationships connection one DOI to another, and also outwards from DOIs to other established and trusted PIDs within the research community, including Open Researcher and Contributor IDs (ORCID) for people, and Research Organisation Registry (ROR) identifiers for institutions, as well as domain specific persistent identifiers such as zbMATH Article Identifiers.

During FAIRCORE4EOSC, work was done to enhance the performance and functionalities of the APIs available for accessing the data, to generate and publish data files of the node metadata and vertices, to develop a statistics reporting tool, and to ingest new data into the graph from project partners.

The PIDGraph helps researchers by exposing the metadata of research outputs for reuse and aggregation by other EOSC partners and services, as well as the wider scholarly community. The addition of datasets containing the links between PIDs enable tracking and reporting of citations and references, alongside other relationships between research outputs.

By leveraging a common schema, the data is easily ingested and by using machine-readable APIs such as GraphQL, integration can be automated, ensuring a streamlined method of working with the PIDGraph data.

Functionalities

The PIDGraph provides several APIs for accessing the data, including a REST API, a GraphQL API, and an OAI-PMH API. In addition, the graph data is regularly published in two datasets, one comprising the metadata for nodes in the graph, and the other containing the vertices of the graph. These services are built on top of DataCite's existing open infrastructure and data.

Access to the graph data is also possible through the web frontend of DataCite Commons, allowing interactive browsing through the data and the visualisation of relationships and metadata aggregations.

Enhancement of the graph data is achieved by the ingestion of metadata from external sources, via dedicated APIs and the common OAI-PMH framework, and the inclusion of PID to PID links from this metadata into the graph.

Usage Statistics reporting for DOIs is made via regular COUNTER-compliant reports to a dedicated service, or by using a JavaScript widget directly on the resource's landing page to submit real-time usage statistics to the PIDGraph.

Impact

By increasing the availability and interoperability of PID metadata, the PIDGraph services help to increase the use and utility of scholarly research outputs and enrich systems and services in the wider community.

By publishing data on the relationships between PIDs, the availability of citation information is enhanced, providing benefit to researchers and institutions.

By ingesting data from other trusted sources, the size and scope of the graph is increased, producing downstream benefits to users of the graph data when working with the PIDGraph services.

Discover the documentation

PIDMR

PID Meta Resolver

Partners working on this component

Component Overview

Persistent identifiers (PIDs) are used in all areas of scientific work. They are not only used for scholarly communication, but also support various data management processes. PIDMR is a generic resolver that makes it possible to resolve PIDs from a wide variety of systems and providers.

The service is active and offers various interfaces for interaction. PID resolution can take place both via a UI and integrated in data processing pipelines. It should be emphasised that, depending on the PID system or provider, either the metadata, the landing page or even the digital object can be delivered directly as the result of the query.

The last option in particular increases the machine processing of digital objects referenced with PID. There are currently around 50 different systems or providers registered. Each provider can register in the service and thus make their own PIDs resolvable via the PIDMR.

Functionalities

The PIDMR service receives a PID in the form of a string and evaluates the assignment to a system or provider. This information is clearly displayed in the UI. After the assignment, the possible methods of resolution, i.e. landing page, metadata or the digital object, are made available for selection.

The request is processed with the submit and the result is displayed to the user. When using APIs, the method can be transferred using a parameter. A detailed description of the API can be found in the documentation. Authentication via the EOSC AAI is available for the registration of new providers.

After successful verification, the provider information is maintained in a database and the PIDs of this provider can be resolved via PIDMR.

Impact

The PIDMR service standardises the resolution of PIDs. Due to the complexity of the current PID landscape, it is very difficult for individual scientists to integrate different PID systems into their workflows. Expert knowledge is no longer required to implement many different interfaces; a well-structured API with clear parameters is now available. The PIDMR service is a scalable and expandable solution that can be integrated into various use cases.

Discover the
PIDMR Service

RAiD

Research Activity Identifier

Partners working on this component

Component Overview

RAiD is a persistent identifier (PID) for research projects and activities that is now in production in Australia and Europe. Governed by ISO Standard 23527:2022 with the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) as the global Registration Authority, RAiD has been successfully implemented in the European context through FAIRCORE4EOSC, with SURF Netherlands serving as the European Registration Agency. The implementation across the European Open Science Cloud demonstrates RAiD's flexibility in different research contexts.

RAiD consists of a unique, resolvable DOI and a metadata record that connects organisations, people, inputs, and outputs to projects. It serves as a container for other PIDs (ORCID, ROR, DOI, etc.), linking research components while tracking project changes over time.

RAiD helps researchers by:

- Reducing administrative burden through automated metadata reuse
- Providing a single source of truth for project information
- Enabling multi-party administration across institutions
- Generating standardised landing pages for project discovery
- Supporting hierarchical relationships between projects
- Tracking project evolution through versioned metadata

RAiD contributes significantly to FAIRCORE4EOSC's PID Graph and RD Graph components, supplying crucial project metadata to Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs). It implements DataCite DOI infrastructure and content negotiation standards, enhancing interoperability with other EOSC PID services.

The RAiD system enables funders to track research outputs and impacts, while research organisations benefit from improved project management and reporting capabilities, making research more transparent by exposing a project's make-up and evolution over time.

Functionalities

RAiD is a persistent identifier system for research projects, combining a unique DOI-based ID with structured metadata. It supports project management through a three-tiered schema (Core, Extended, Local) and allows users to:

- Mint RAiDs via web app or API
- Link projects to components using PIDs (ORCID, ROR, DOI, etc.)
- Track project evolution with versioning
- Assign access permissions for collaborative editing
- Resolve RAiDs to standardised landing pages
- Access metadata via API in multiple formats

RAiD is operated by Registration Agencies using RAiD Service Software, which includes a React-based web interface and a Java-based API. DOI minting is implemented via DataCite, with secure authentication from multiple identity providers. The metadata model is purpose-built for research projects.

The distributed architecture supports global adoption while ensuring centralised resolution through raid.org. Registration Agencies retain local control, including the ability to customise Extended metadata and define Local metadata fields, ensuring flexibility and global discoverability.

Impact

RAiD addresses a gap in the PID ecosystem, transforming research management across the entire research landscape.

For researchers, RAiD reduces administrative burden by reducing redundant data entry, improves project metadata accuracy, and supports research integrity through comprehensive tracking of project evolution. Research organisations benefit from enhanced reporting, improved collaboration, and strategic intelligence about research activities.

Funders can see the outcomes and impacts of their investments, with tracking extending beyond usual grant reporting in time and scope.

By connecting diverse research components through the PID Graph, RAiD enables comprehensive analysis of the research ecosystem, informing evidence-based policy development.

As adoption grows globally, RAiD will establish a universal language for describing research projects, fostering international collaboration and enabling more sophisticated research assessment.

Discover the RAiD Service

RDGraph

Research Discovery Graph

Partners working on this component

Component Overview

The EOSC Research Discovery Graph Service (RDGraph) delivers advanced discovery tools across EOSC resources and communities. The RDGraph builds upon the EOSC catalogue's content, extending it with additional entities like the Research Activity Identifiers (RAiDs). It offers a variety of advanced functionalities exploiting several intelligent community-oriented discovery tools developed by the partners of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project.

The respective toolset includes natural language processing and graph-based cutting-edge solutions for EOSC users to search and discover research entities (publications, data, software) by exploiting their context of creation and reuse. Context includes aspects such as disciplines, regions, institutions, funders, projects, researchers, RAiDs, and EOSC services. The RDGraph will be made accessible via UI/UX tools, regular data dumps and APIs to support third-party service interoperability via EOSC interoperability frameworks and data re-use to service.

Functionalities

The RDGraph component:

- Ensures that the RDGraph is regularly updated with scholarly content from various providers by developing appropriate provision workflows
- Provides regular data dumps of the RDGraph
- Provides APIs to support data re-use and third-party service interoperability
- Empowers users to search and perform queries using keywords and Natural Language
- Facilitates the discovery of products and services by exploiting impact-based indicators for ranking search results
- Enables filtering of search results based on citation-based impact indicators
- Enables community members to get personalised recommendations for research products
- Suggests unregistered RAiDs aiming to facilitate EOSC users to manage and track related activities
- Enables the connection with the EOSC RAiD service/registry
- Supports the discovery of research products and services in the RDGraph through the Discovery Portal

Impact

RDGraph improves the user experience of researchers and other stakeholders in EOSC to discover scientific knowledge by providing a flexible and federated search service that extends EOSC Research Catalogue. As a result, it is expected to contribute to the acceleration of scientific knowledge production processes.

Discover the
RDGraph

RSAC

Research Software APIs & Connectors

Partners working on this component

Software Heritage

Component Overview

The Research Software APIs and Connectors (RSAC) developed in FAIRCORE4EOSC enable research infrastructures to preserve, describe, and cite software by connecting directly to the Software Heritage archive. Using the CodeMeta metadata standard and Software Heritage identifiers (SWHIDs), these services ensure software artefacts can be reliably referenced and integrated into scholarly workflows.

The design of the RSAC components was guided by the 2021 Scholarly Infrastructures of Research Software (SIRS) report, which called for actionable improvements in how software is handled within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and academia. FAIRCORE4EOSC brought together several of the infrastructures featured in the report to implement these recommendations.

RSAC components are now available for:

- **Repositories:** InvenioRDM (CERN) and DANS Dataverse (DANS-KNAW) offer integration for metadata and code deposits.
- **Publishers:** Dagstuhl (LZI) and Episciences (INRIA) enable citation and linking in submissions.
- **Aggregators:** swMATH (FIZ) and OpenAIRE provide software archiving and metadata enrichment.

These integrations enhance the visibility, reuse, and citation of research software, supporting a more robust and FAIR-aligned research ecosystem.

Functionalities

The FAIRCORE4EOSC project developed APIs and connectors to integrate scholarly repositories, open access publishers, and aggregators with Software Heritage. These connections support the archival, reference, description, and citation of research software.

For scholarly repositories, connectors enable the deposit of software artifacts into Software Heritage, the retrieval of SWHIDs, and the display of these identifiers within local records. Repositories can also exchange curated metadata and export citations in formats such as BibLaTeX, CSL, and codemeta.json.

For open-access publishers, the integration automates the archival of software associated with research articles. It ensures SWHIDs are displayed in publication records and supports the deposit and retrieval of metadata and preferred citation information in multiple formats.

For aggregators, connectors allow the detection of software references in articles and trigger the archiving of source code missing from Software Heritage. Aggregators expose the resulting SWHIDs, deposit and retrieve metadata, and provide citation exports in standard formats. Together, these developments make software easier to archive, discover, and cite, aligning with FAIR principles and improving research reproducibility.

Impact

The RSAC component enhances interoperability among scholarly infrastructures by operationalising the four pillars of the SIRS report: Archive, Reference, Describe, and Cite. It enables repositories, publishers, and aggregators to archive software artefacts in Software Heritage, reference them using persistent SWHIDs, and describe them using the CodeMeta vocabulary. The interoperability guidelines developed for RSAC connectors promote the use of standardised citation formats, such as biblatex-software. By supporting consistent metadata exchange and persistent identification, RSAC facilitates reproducibility, discoverability, and proper recognition of research software within scholarly workflows. This targeted effort lays the foundation for treating software as a first-class research output, advancing its integration into the scholarly communication ecosystem.

Discover the
RSAC Service

SWHM

Software Heritage Mirror

Partners working on this component

Component Overview

To safeguard against information loss and streamline access to the collective software knowledge, Software Heritage has developed a network of mirrors. A mirror is a read-only replica of the Software Heritage archive — a comprehensive, ever-growing collection of publicly available source code from around the world. One such mirror, hosted by GRNET in Greece, was deployed during the FAIRCORE4EOSC project and is now fully operational. GRNET's Mirror functions as a complete and independently managed copy of the Software Heritage archive. It operates in agreement with, yet independently from, the Software Heritage organization, while remaining fully synchronized.

For researchers, the presence of GRNET's Mirror offers significant advantages. This addition to the Software Heritage Mirror network supports the mission of the Software Heritage organisation by providing geographically closer access points. It therefore reduces latency, and improves download speeds, enabling smoother and faster exploration of software histories. Researchers can trace the evolution of code, verify published results, and reuse legacy software in new contexts—all with confidence that the information will remain accessible over time. Beyond immediate research needs, GRNET's Mirror also reinforces the long-term preservation of digital knowledge.

By distributing copies of the archive, they offer redundancy and resilience against data loss, whether due to technical failure or geopolitical events. In doing so, they support the mission of Software Heritage: to collect, preserve, and share the source code that underpins modern science, technology, and culture.

Functionalities

GRNET's Mirror of the Software Heritage Archive (MSHA) is a read-only replica of the main Software Heritage Archive, designed to provide public access to ingested source code. While it does not support all features of the main platform, it offers essential functionalities that make the archive accessible and useful to the research and developer communities.

The Mirror enables users to browse the archive through a web-based interface, allowing exploration of the vast collection of source code snapshots. It also supports search by origin URL, helping users locate the exact repositories or code origins archived over time. Additionally, it provides limited access to the public API, allowing programmatic queries for metadata and code content, though usage is rate-limited.

Synchronization with the main archive occurs constantly, ensuring the mirror remains largely current, with only minor delays depending on the volume and timing of new data ingested. By offering regional access to core features, GRNET's Mirror enhances availability, reduces access latency, and contributes to the robustness and redundancy of the global Software Heritage preservation infrastructure.

Impact

GRNET's Mirror is a new addition to the global Software Heritage network, designed to preserve and ensure open access to software source code. It strengthens software availability, protects against data loss, and guarantees that critical digital knowledge remains accessible to all. As an onboarded service to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), the GRNET's Mirror supports the open sharing and discovery of research software across Europe. This important step was made possible through the support of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, which funded the deployment of the mirror.

Discover the
SWHM Service

FAIRCORE4EOSC

Core Components Supporting a FAIR EOSC

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